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DEVELOPMENT OF HERITAGE-BASED EXCURSION ACTIVITIES IN THE BUKHARA REGION

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Abstract. This article examines the current excursion practices in the Bukhara region, with particular emphasis on its historical sites, and draws upon European standards as a benchmark for improving the quality and attractiveness of excursion services. The Bukhara region is home to a remarkable collection of historical and architectural landmarks that possess significant cultural, religious, and economic value for the city. In recent years, the volume of excursion activities and the number of international visitors have steadily increased. However, to further enhance tourist satisfaction, encourage longer stays, and strengthen Bukhara's position as a competitive cultural tourism destination, several improvements are required. These include the implementation of advanced technologies, the modernization and enrichment of tour programs, the improvement of tour guides' professional competencies, and the more effective integration of local cultural heritage into excursion itineraries.

Key words: excursion services, cultural heritage, tour guiding, excursion sites, historical monuments, tourism statistics, European standards, modern technologies, promotional content.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada Buxoro viloyatida mavjud ekskursiya amaliyotlari tahlil qilinib, tarixiy obyektlarga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi hamda ekskursiya xizmatlari sifati va jozibadorligini oshirishda Yevropa standartlari mezon sifatida qo'llaniladi. Buxoro viloyati shahar uchun muhim madaniy, diniy va iqtisodiy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan ko'plab tarixiy-me'moriy yodgorliklarga boy hudud hisoblanadi. So'nggi yillarda hududda ekskursiya faoliyati hajmi hamda xorijiy sayyohlar soni barqaror ravishda oshib bormoqda. Shu bilan birga, sayyohlar qoniqishini yanada oshirish, ularning tashrif muddatini uzaytirish hamda Buxoroning raqobatbardosh madaniy turizm markazi sifatidagi mavqeini mustahkamlash maqsadida qator takomillashtirish choralari zarur. Jumladan, zamonaviy texnologiyalarni joriy etish, ekskursiya dasturlarini yangilash va boyitish, gidlarning kasbiy malakasini oshirish hamda mahalliy madaniy merosni ekskursiya marshrutlariga samarali integratsiya qilish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ekskursiya xizmatlari, madaniy meros, gidlik xizmati, ekskursiya obyektlari, tarixiy yodgorliklar, turizm statistikasi, Yevropa standartlari, zamonaviy texnologiyalar, targ'ibot materiali.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются существующие практики экскурсионной деятельности в Бухарском регионе с акцентом на исторические объекты, а также рассматриваются европейские стандарты как ориентир для повышения качества и привлекательности экскурсионных услуг. Бухарский регион обладает значительным количеством историко-архитектурных памятников, имеющих важное культурное, религиозное и экономическое значение для города. В последние годы наблюдается устойчивый рост объема экскурсионной деятельности и числа иностранных туристов. Вместе с тем для дальнейшего повышения удовлетворенности туристов, увеличения продолжительности их пребывания и укрепления позиций Бухары как конкурентоспособного центра культурного туризма требуется реализация ряда мер. К ним относятся внедрение современных технологий, модернизация и обогащение экскурсионных программ, повышение профессиональной квалификации гидов, а также более эффективная интеграция местного культурного наследия в экскурсионные маршруты.

Ключевые слова: экскурсионные услуги, культурное наследие, услуги гида, экскурсионные объекты, исторические памятники, туристическая статистика, европейские стандарты, современные технологии, рекламные материалы.

INTRODUCTION

Many countries present their rich history and cultural heritage as a foundation for tourism development. Similarly, Bukhara is one of the largest historical regions of Uzbekistan, distinguished by its unique architectural and spiritual legacy. According to the UNESCO World Heritage Centre, Bukhara is situated along the Silk Road and has a history spanning more than 2,000 years [16]. As noted by Kasimova Feruza in the article "Tourist Attractions in Bukhara and Their Cultural Significance," the city is often referred to as "Ancient Bukhara" and "Bukhara Sharif," which reflects its historically significant role in spiritual and educational life in the East [2].

Official cultural heritage records indicate that Bukhara contains approximately 829 tangible cultural heritage objects under state protection, including 507 architectural monuments and 287 archaeological sites, as well as other categories such as monumental art and local heritage attractions [14]. Among the most prominent historical monuments are the Poi Kalyan complex (comprising the Kalyan Minaret, Kalyan Mosque, and Miri Arab Madrasah), the Ark Fortress, the Samanid Mausoleum, Chor Minor Madrasah, the Labi-Hauz ensemble, and the Magoki-Attori Mosque. These monuments represent outstanding examples of Central Asian Islamic architecture and reflect the region's centuries-old cultural evolution.

These historical monuments play a significant role in Bukhara's economic development and cultural identity. In recent years, Uzbekistan has adopted several presidential decrees and legislative acts aimed at developing tourism and fundamentally improving its quality. For example, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Tourism" (adopted by the Oliy Majlis on 16-04-2019 and approved by the Senate on 21-06-2019) outlines key measures, including:

1. the development of domestic tourism, particularly social tourism, and the creation of favorable conditions for organizing tourism and excursions for children, youth, the elderly, persons with disabilities, and low-income groups;
2. the training, retraining, and professional development of tour guides;
3. ensuring the safety of tourists and excursionists, as well as the protection of their rights, freedoms, and property [3].

Furthermore, according to Presidential Decision PQ-135 dated 26-04-2023, tourism potential and excursion services in the Kagan and Romitan districts of the Bukhara region are being actively promoted and developed [15]. As the popularity of historical sites increases, the demand for high-quality excursion services and professionally trained guides correspondingly grows.

Regarding the conceptual understanding of excursions, Khayrullayeva N.N., in her article "Innovative Ways of Improving Excursion Service around Touristic Destinations," defines an excursion (derived from the Latin word *excursio*, meaning "journey") as an organized and guided process of exploring the surrounding environment through prepared objects, themes, and routes under the supervision of a qualified specialist [3]. Excursion services represent a complex educational and interpretative activity rather than merely the delivery of informational content. Thematic excursions differ from general city tours in terms of content structure, thematic focus, and methodological complexity. Historically, excursions evolved from simple field trips aimed at collecting medicinal plants or museum specimens into structured educational and cultural programs.

Significant measures have also been undertaken to improve the system of training and professional development of tour guides. In particular, as part of national initiatives to enhance personnel training, the Association of Guides of Uzbekistan was officially established on 20-02-2019 under the leadership of Abdulaziz Aqkulov, the First Deputy Chairman of the State Committee for Tourism Development, and was granted official certification [3].

The purpose of this article is to improve excursion services at historical monuments in the Bukhara region by strengthening the professional competencies of guides, integrating modern technologies into excursion practices, increasing tourist satisfaction, and enhancing the overall tourism potential and competitiveness of the region.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Cultural heritage tourism has long been recognized as a significant driver of economic development and the preservation of cultural identity. Timothy and Boyd (2003) define heritage tourism as a branch of tourism focused on experiencing the past, whereby destinations utilize their historical, architectural, and natural heritage assets to attract visitors. Foundational research emphasizes that the authenticity and integrity of heritage sites are critical determinants of tourist satisfaction and the long-term sustainability of heritage destinations [5].

Expanding upon this perspective, McKercher and du Cros (2002) propose a matrix model of cultural tourism, arguing that the depth of experience sought by tourists varies considerably. Consequently, site managers must strike a balance between conservation objectives and visitor engagement strategies. These theoretical insights are directly applicable to Bukhara, which hosts more than 800 protected heritage objects, ranging from examples of Islamic architecture to Silk Road archaeological sites [6].

The designation of Bukhara as a UNESCO World Heritage Site in 1993 significantly enhanced its global tourism profile [7]. Ashworth and Tunbridge (2000) contend that World Heritage listing functions as a powerful tourism brand, increasing international visibility while simultaneously raising the risk of over-tourism and commercialization. For Bukhara, this dual dynamic implies that excursion services must not only attract a growing number of visitors but also ensure the long-term preservation and integrity of historical monuments. Fariza (2025) reinforces this argument by highlighting the cultural significance of Bukhara's major attractions and advocating for more structured and interpretive excursion services that effectively communicate the spiritual and historical depth of sites such as the Poi Kalyan complex and the Ark Fortress [2].

The integration of digital technologies into tourism services has fundamentally transformed visitor experiences worldwide. Tussyadiah et al. (2018) conducted an empirical study on virtual reality (VR) applications and found that immersive VR experiences significantly enhance tourists' sense of presence, attitudes, and behavioral intentions to visit actual destinations. These findings are particularly relevant to heritage tourism, where VR can function both as a promotional instrument and as a preservation tool by enabling virtual access to fragile or restricted heritage sites [8].

Similarly, Jung et al. (2016) demonstrate that augmented reality (AR) applications in heritage contexts improve visitors' understanding and overall satisfaction, indicating that technology-mediated interpretation provides measurable educational value [9].

Within the framework of smart tourism destinations, Buhalis and Amaranggana (2015) explain how the Internet of Things (IoT) facilitates real-time data collection, dynamic service personalization, and efficient management of tourist flows. They argue that interconnected digital infrastructure enables destination managers to respond proactively to visitor demand, thereby improving both satisfaction and sustainability [10]. This approach aligns with proposals developed at Bukhara State University recommending the installation of visitor-counting technologies at heritage sites to optimize flow management.

Gretzel et al. (2015) further conceptualize smart tourism as an ecosystem that integrates ICT platforms, big data analytics, and stakeholder networks to generate enhanced tourism value [11]. Building upon this global discourse, Nabijonova examines the applicability of VR, artificial intelligence (AI), QR codes, and IoT technologies within Uzbekistan's tourism sector. In particular, she notes that QR-based multilingual information systems at heritage sites can substantially increase accessibility for diverse visitor groups at relatively low implementation costs [12].

Regarding artificial intelligence, Ukpabi and Karjaluo (2017) review the impact of AI-driven technologies, including recommendation engines and chatbots, on tourists' behavioral intentions and perceptions of service quality. Their meta-analysis identifies responsiveness, personalization, and informational accuracy as the most valued attributes of AI-based systems. These characteristics can be effectively realized through multilingual AI assistants proposed for implementation at Bukhara's heritage sites [13].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The primary research method employed in this study was a comprehensive analysis of scientific, technical, and statistical sources related to tourism development and excursion services. In addition, empirical insights were obtained through academic discussions and proposal-based sessions conducted with students of Bukhara State University.

Recent analytical findings indicate that one of the priority tasks in the Bukhara region is to increase the number of multilingual guides in the tourism and excursion sector, as well as to expand the application of modern technologies within heritage sites. The effective implementation of these measures is expected not only to strengthen Bukhara's tourism potential but also to contribute significantly to the overall development of Uzbekistan's tourism industry, thereby generating sustainable economic benefits.

Several roundtable discussions organized among students of Bukhara State University resulted in a number of constructive proposals aimed at enhancing tourism management and service quality. One of the key recommendations was the installation of modern technological systems, such as "Heritage Site Visitor Counter" devices, at major historical monuments. These systems would enable accurate recording and monitoring of tourist flows, facilitating data-driven decision-making and improving visitor management.

Considering that excursion services in the Bukhara region are currently offered predominantly in English, Russian, and French, it was proposed to expand multilingual services to accommodate tourists from a broader range of countries. Suggested languages include Chinese, Korean, Hindi, Japanese, Spanish, Portuguese, and others. Furthermore, emphasis was placed on creating professional development opportunities for young guides who possess proficiency in these languages. This involves structured training programs to ensure that guides can accurately and effectively communicate Bukhara's historical heritage and cultural values in languages accessible to international visitors.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the contemporary global economy, tourism and excursion services play a decisive role in the socio-economic development of many countries. Revenue generated from tourism constitutes a significant share of national income in numerous developed economies. In order to maintain competitive advantages and improve tourism performance indicators, leading European countries such as France, Spain, Italy, the United Kingdom, and Germany continuously modernize their technological infrastructure and service delivery systems. As emphasized by Nabijonova Shohida in her study entitled "The Potential of Innovation and Modern Technology in the Tourism Sector," technologies such as virtual reality (VR), artificial intelligence (AI), QR codes, and the Internet of Things (IoT) are fundamentally transforming the tourism industry and are widely utilized in developed countries [17]. The adoption of these technologies in Bukhara, in accordance with European standards, can significantly enhance the quality, efficiency, and accessibility of tourism and excursion services.

Virtual reality enables tourists to explore destinations digitally before actual travel and contributes to cultural preservation by offering virtual access to fragile historical sites. In Uzbekistan, VR can be applied to create immersive digital tours of key heritage destinations such as Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva, as well as to enrich museum exhibitions through interactive visualization. Artificial intelligence enhances tourism services through personalization, automation, and data-driven analytics. AI-powered systems can provide multilingual customer support, intelligent travel recommendations, smart itinerary planning, and tourism demand forecasting. In Bukhara, the implementation of multilingual AI assistants and predictive analytics tools can improve visitor engagement and operational management. QR codes represent a cost-effective and easily deployable solution for delivering multilingual historical information, maps, and audio guides at heritage sites. The Internet of Things facilitates real-time monitoring of visitor flows, smart transportation management, and integrated hospitality services. The combined application of VR, AI, QR codes, and IoT technologies can substantially modernize Bukhara's tourism infrastructure and strengthen Uzbekistan's international competitiveness in the heritage tourism market.

Despite the importance of technological innovation, tourism development cannot be conceptualized without professional guides and structured excursion services. Guides play a crucial role in organizing excursions, ensuring participant safety, and delivering interpretative content that shapes tourists' understanding of cultural heritage. Beyond their operational function, guides perform an essential pedagogical role. As noted by Davronov Istamkhuja Olimovich in his research on improving excursion services, the excursion process can be regarded as a pedagogical interaction in which the guide transmits structured knowledge based on thematic interpretation while participants actively engage with and internalize this information [1]. Professional competence in guiding requires subject expertise, analytical and figurative thinking, understanding of visitor psychology, group management skills, mastery of pedagogical techniques, and professional intuition. Excursions therefore contribute not only to tourism consumption but also to educational, moral, and aesthetic development, positioning excursion services as an important component of non-formal education.

The introduction of "Heritage Site Visitor Counter" technologies at historical monuments would provide reliable statistical data on visitor flows, enabling more effective tourism management. By identifying the most and least visited attractions, local authorities can conduct targeted surveys at under-visited sites to detect deficiencies and implement improvement strategies. Redirecting tourist flows toward lesser-known monuments

would reduce overcrowding at popular landmarks, promote balanced spatial distribution, and potentially extend tourists' length of stay. Additionally, organizing complementary cultural and recreational events, such as marathons, festivals, or sports competitions, may increase visitor engagement and overall tourism expenditure, thereby contributing to national economic growth.

Expanding multilingual excursion services beyond English, Russian, and French to include languages such as Chinese, Korean, Hindi, Japanese, Spanish, and Portuguese is expected to generate substantial benefits. Providing services in additional languages would significantly enhance accessibility and comprehension for international visitors, attract new tourism markets—particularly from Asia and Latin America—and increase revenue for tour operators, hotels, restaurants, and local businesses. This strategy would also create employment opportunities for multilingual guides and strengthen Bukhara's reputation as a globally accessible cultural destination. Although such expansion may present operational challenges, including the need for qualified personnel, translation of materials, and coordinated scheduling, the long-term benefits—such as improved tourist satisfaction, enhanced international visibility, and deeper intercultural exchange—clearly outweigh the constraints. Furthermore, as demonstrated by Valeria Provotorina in her study on innovation-based development of vocational education in tourism and excursion activities, innovative educational technologies are essential in professional training systems, as they enhance competency development and ensure systematic knowledge transfer [4].

Overall, the integration of advanced digital technologies, the strengthening of professional guiding competencies, the implementation of visitor flow management systems, and the expansion of multilingual services collectively represent a strategic pathway for modernizing Bukhara's tourism sector. This integrated approach enhances service quality, promotes sustainable heritage management, increases tourist satisfaction, and positions Bukhara as a competitive and forward-looking cultural tourism destination on the global stage.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the development and enhancement of excursion services based on historical monuments in the Bukhara region play a pivotal role in strengthening the city's position as a leading cultural tourism destination. Bukhara possesses a rich concentration of historical and architectural heritage, which functions not only as a valuable cultural asset but also as a significant driver of economic growth through tourism activities. However, in order to fully realize this potential, traditional excursion practices must be modernized and aligned with international—particularly European—standards.

The findings of this study demonstrate that the integration of modern digital technologies, including Virtual Reality (VR), Artificial Intelligence (AI), QR codes, and Internet of Things (IoT) solutions, can substantially improve the quality, accessibility, and attractiveness of excursion services. These technologies enhance visitor engagement, provide multilingual and interactive interpretative content, and support efficient management of tourist flows at historical sites. At the same time, the research confirms that technological innovation alone is insufficient without highly qualified and professionally trained guides. Guides remain central actors in the excursion process, performing not only informative functions but also educational and pedagogical roles that contribute to visitors' deeper understanding of cultural heritage.

Furthermore, the expansion of excursion services into additional foreign languages and the systematic training of young multilingual guides will enable Bukhara to access new international tourism markets and increase overall tourist satisfaction. The implementation of visitor monitoring systems and data-driven decision-making mechanisms can contribute to a more balanced distribution of tourists between highly popular and lesser-known heritage sites, thereby extending the average length of stay and increasing economic returns.

Overall, the combined application of advanced technologies, professional guide development, multilingual service expansion, and strategic visitor management constitutes a sustainable framework for improving excursion services in the Bukhara region. The implementation of these measures will enhance the overall tourist experience, strengthen Bukhara's international competitiveness, and contribute to the long-term development of Uzbekistan's tourism sector, while ensuring the preservation of its invaluable historical and cultural heritage.

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